

“MORE THAN WHAT I CAN OFFER”: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF ALTRUISTIC PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS IN LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

Teachers, often referred to as “secondary parents,” sometimes go beyond their professional duties, dedicating their personal resources to support less privileged students. Altruism, though a selfless concern for the well-being of others without expectation of reciprocation can still come at a personal cost. Grounded in Batson's (1991) Empathy-Altruism Theory, the research utilized Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) to deeply understand the personal experiences of altruistic public-school teachers (APTs) in Laguna. The findings revealed that APTs are primarily motivated by empathy, personal struggles, and a strong sense of responsibility to address their students' emotional and other personal needs. However, their altruistic behaviors lead to emotional exhaustion, financial strain, and relational complexities. Despite these challenges, teachers exhibit resilience by adopting coping strategies such as collaboration, emotional management, and seeking support from others. In response to these findings, the researchers propose the *Altruistic Teacher Assistance (ALTA)*—an adaptable framework that stakeholders such as Department of Education (DepEd) and school administrators can implement. ALTA includes structured recognition, mental health support, peer mentoring, and wellness initiatives to promote teacher well-being. The study underscores the urgent need for systemic reforms to ensure consistent support, address burnout, and sustain altruistic behavior.

Keywords: *altruism, empathy, burnout, sacrifice, public-school teachers well-being.*

INTRODUCTION

In Filipino culture, there is a profound emphasis on the education of children (Alampay & Garcia, 2019). This reflects the societal conviction that education's transformative power is the key to securing a child's future for a better life. And while education alleviates poverty by solutions such as increasing economic growth and reducing income inequality, a complicated issue is that poverty and education are inextricably linked. This means that although education provides a pathway out of poverty, there are also barriers within education that are primarily caused by poverty. Students frequently arrive at school unprepared, hungry, and lacking home support, prompting teacher concerns about poverty's impact on education. Recognizing this issue, 67% of teachers are prepared to offer support to students living in poverty, which means that the education profession involves not only the systematic teaching of information to students but also a dedication to contributing to the welfare of humanity (Ghent, 2020). Helping others and bearing that responsibility are the most satisfying aspects of the teaching profession, aligning with the concept of altruism or the act of helping others without any thought of personal gain, as cited by Palta (2019).

In the context of the Philippines, a developing nation, such dedication is crucial. A significant portion of the population, including students in public schools, encounter socio-economic challenges that may influence educational outcomes. Such factors include compromised academic performance, decreased retention rates, and behavioral changes in school (Bradley, 2022).

While teachers act as "secondary parents" and a public servant, educators may feel a considerable amount of concern regarding the future trajectories of these students' lives, particularly on how it will affect their overall well-being. Hence, educators tend to go beyond conventional role as 'teachers,' demonstrating altruistic behaviors, such as dedicating significant personal resources to support less privileged students, even at personal expenses (Palta, 2019). Despite the prevalence of altruistic behaviors among teachers, particularly in resource-constrained settings, a lack of research exists on exploring unique experiences within the Philippine public school system, indicating a significant gap in research. Thus, this underscores the necessity for further research on the subject. By exploring the lived experiences of altruistic public-school teachers in Laguna, this study aims to provide valuable insights into their motivations, challenges, and potential areas of support, contributing to a deeper understanding of the realities faced by public school teachers to support students in the Philippines and hopefully spur more research in this field.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded on Empathy-Altruism hypothesis which illustrates how a sense of empathy disposition towards another person leads to performing altruistic behaviors that enhance other person's well-being. Proposed in 1991 by Daniel Batson, a social psychologist, this theory provides an answer to the question— *perhaps people can sometimes sacrifice themselves for other people, and not only for themselves?* (Batson et al., 2015). Despite decades of scrutiny, the study suggests that the empathy-altruism hypothesis may have a dual impact. It proposes that while it can benefit individuals and society, it can also have unintended consequences.

The researchers hypothesized that due to empathy for their students and considering the close interpersonal relationship between teachers and students, this empathy—characterized by feelings of sympathy, tenderness, and warmth—drives teachers' altruistic behaviors. This means they often extend their roles beyond professional duties to help their less privileged students. According to the theory, such actions can be beneficial by helping the student yet may also be detrimental to the teacher if their personal investment in fulfilling students' needs becomes counterproductive to their personal well-being.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to explore the lived experiences of altruistic public-school teachers in Laguna.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What ways have public-school teachers gone beyond their usual roles to help their students?
2. What drives the public-school teachers to commit altruistic behaviors toward their students?
3. What are the challenges associated with altruistic behaviors exhibited by public school teachers?
4. How do public-school teachers handle the challenges associated with altruistic behaviors?
5. What emerging themes can be identified from the gathered data?
6. Based on the findings, what framework may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In light of the above objective formulated in this study, qualitative research was used in making the findings and conclusions which included exploring their experiences, motivations, and behaviors.

Specifically, the study used an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), a qualitative method that is used to understand people's lived experiences, to be able to explore the meanings that individuals make of their experiences (Fieldsend & Smith, 2021). Hence, it allowed the researchers to analyze the self-reports of public-school teachers that drive them towards altruism, going through their perspectives and narratives that shaped their behavior beyond professional matters.

Research Participants

The study involved five (5) participants of any gender as high levels of empathy mean that there is a greater chance for an individual to be an altruist irrespective of their gender (Ferrer et al., 2019). These individuals were public school teachers who exhibit altruistic behavior or referred in this study as “APSTs” with at least 5-10 years of teaching experience. Long work experience exposes teachers to a wider range of situations and challenges that can shape their approach to helping others. They must also reside in Laguna. The individuals need to meet the particular criteria before being selected to participate in this study.

Furthermore, APSTs are known for their selfless dedication to students, going beyond their conventional role as teachers to help and support them through difficulties despite challenges such as possibly limited resources and recognition, maintaining a strong commitment to their student’s well-being. Further criteria were included whether they consistently engaged within the following: used personal resources to assist students (*e.g. providing school supplies, meals, transportation*), *engaged in other acts of going beyond the call of duty to help students (e.g. mentoring, personal counseling)*.

Sampling Technique

A combination of purposive and snowball sampling was used in this study. Snowball sampling, a purposeful method, starts with known individuals and relies on their referrals to reach others with similar characteristics. This approach complements purposive sampling, where researchers actively seek participants who meet specific criteria.

Research Locale

The study was conducted among public-school teachers in Laguna, a province in the CALABARZON region of Luzon, due to its diverse educational landscape and representation of the challenges faced by educators in the region. This locale was chosen to gain context-specific insights into the local educational setting.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection was a semi-structured interview directed with open-ended questions. To ensure its validity, the researchers first went through an internal review process with their research adviser. Three (3) professionals (Psychometricians) with expertise relevant to the study further validated the interview questions. Upon successful verification, the researchers were issued a certificate verifying their instrument. Until then, the adjustments and alterations suggested by the validators were included in formulating the instrument and then prepared for distribution.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers asked for informed consent from the five (5) participants before they conducted the interview. In conducting the semi-structured interviews, open-ended questions were utilized, the location, and time for the interview was determined by the researcher in consultation with the participant. The interview responses were in the form of audiovisual recordings to capture participant's narrative. Following that, the collected data were transcribed, and all the research undertook the analysis of the collected data with the intention of looking at some unique findings to be able to see the pattern and themes that have emerged.

Data Analysis

Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis or IPA was utilized in this study in order to explore the different experiences of the participants. According to Fieldsend and Smith (2021), this approach allowed the researchers to delve deeper into the participants' world—their personal experiences and perception of the things around them.

The process involved reading the transcribed data multiple times for the sake of: (1) familiarizing with the participants' use of language and (2) finding more abstract and psychology-related terms. Second, upon collecting themes, it was clustered based on their connection with each other. It involved listing identified themes, reorganizing them based on connection and uniqueness, checking whether the themes go well with the participants' original words, creating a table and dropping themes which might not be relevant. Third, these steps will be repeated and be applied to other participants' cases. Lastly, these themes were then translated and compiled into narrative accounts—to be related to existing literature and studies and using the verbatim transcripts that helped distinguish the participants' words and the researcher's analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Consent was given willfully and voluntarily, requiring participants to understand the questions and be competent in their state. This implies that they have the liberty to decline the interview process. Each participant was approached individually, then were provided with a detailed explanation of the research process, purpose of the study, including the data collection process. Thus, a generous amount of time was also given to ask necessary questions, and the researchers were open to addressing any of their research-related concerns. Finally, the researchers asked for their respective consents to record the interview session.

Furthermore, the researchers guaranteed that the participants' identities will remain anonymous and will be confidentially protected throughout the entire recruitment and interview processes. The interviews were conducted in a quiet room, and measures will be taken to discourage any unauthorized individuals from accessing the room with the interviewing progress. Participants had the right to decline the interview and if for any reason he or she feels the interview is intrusive then the interview can be declined. Voice recordings generated from transcription were secured and stored to prevent data leakage,

while interview data will be deleted after three days of use for transcription to negate leakage of data. All of these are associated with the Republic Act No. 10173 referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (DPA) of the Philippines.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data, highlighting key findings and their implications. The following tables outline central themes and sub-themes from the collected data analyzed through thematic analysis.

It is also important to take note that some of the themes that emerged without a pattern or commonality among other participants was a deliberate decision to include by the researchers. While thematic analysis often emphasizes recurring statements to form cohesive themes, as cited by McLeod (2024), themes are substantiated not just by their prevalence but by their ability to illuminate things that matter. Hence, the incorporation of unique themes allowed the researchers to present more comprehensive and richer understandings of altruistic public school teachers' lived experiences by ensuring even unique but significant points of view are considered.

RQ1. WAYS PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS HAVE GONE BEYOND THEIR USUAL ROLES

Central Theme 1: Financial and Material Sacrifice

Going beyond the supposed role of a teacher would mean sacrificing something for the sake of helping a student, even if it is giving and providing things that are no longer required in the sole task description of a teacher.

Sub-theme 1.1 Financial and Material Support

This theme pertains to the altruistic behavior of a teacher to aid a student by means of the provision of the internal support. This is evident in the APST's statements like those of APST1 who described how teachers are often pushed to bring money out of their own pockets to support students.

["Sa public schools, paminsan-minsan, depende sa school, may budget, minsan wala. Kaya, kailangan talaga huhugot ka sa bulsa mo."] – APST1

Strengthening the idea that altruistic teachers often use their own money for giving out help, APST2 shared that a large portion of their salary goes to helping their students more than being used for their personal or familial needs.

["Salary ko ay hindi na pang pamilya, hindi na pang pamilya talaga. Kundi pang malaking bahagi na napupunta talaga sa mga estudyante ko."] – APST2

Furthermore, APST2 would also often buys students with food in order for them not to get jealous to their peers who are more privileged.

["Nagbibigay ako ng pagkain sa kanila, dahil nakikita ko na naiinggit sila sa kanilang mga kaklase kapag kumakain sila at wala silang pagkain."] – **APST2**

Doan et al. (2024) shed more light on the great personal efforts of teachers, especially those in the service of many. With limited resources, teachers have made and continue to make significant personal sacrifices. When parents are unable to meet students' needs for food, shelter supplies and clothes and other necessities of life teachers often use their own money to buy the necessities. This practice comes from a positive obligation to provide students with equal chances. Such findings support the fact that APSTs are selfless by trying to support students' welfare and the promotion for equality among less privileged ones.

Central Theme 2: Personal Time Sacrifice

This theme reflects the altruistic nature of public-school teachers who are willing to dedicate their time and energy to support students beyond the classroom. It emphasizes their commitment to addressing students' emotional and personal needs, often at the expense of their own time, highlighting the depth of their care and responsibility in fostering students' well-being.

Sub-theme 5.1 Provision of Guidance and Support

Just like any other employee or worker, a teacher, aside from being a teacher, also has their own private time to spend as a break from their jobs. This often includes spending time with their families or having their own 'me-time' as a form of rest and relaxation. But according to APST5, their duties as teachers often coincide with this personal time.

["Even though it was a time when he should have been with his family, and I should have been spending it with mine, I sacrificed a few days of my vacation to personally meet with him because I knew he needed support and guidance during that difficult time."] – **APST5**

In the article by Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2018), the authors examined the consequences of teacher workload and role demands on personal time. They discovered that teachers give their own time to ensure that they offer emotional support direction to learners. The research discovered that high levels of job satisfaction come from being burnt out due to offering personal time. Interviewed teachers have said things like this: "It is not just a career; it is an obligation to be there to serve the students, even if the service offends my own right" illustrating the deep sense of duty and selflessness that drives them to sacrifice their personal time for the well-being of their students.

Moreover, Forbes (2022) examines aspects of a teacher's personality and activities, such as the desire to change the world and their involvement in non-teaching tasks. These include offering comfort to students during emergencies or dedicating extra time to students who may be struggling.

Central Theme 3: Parental Role Sacrifice

It highlights the level of dedication and service exhibited by altruistic public-school teachers who tend to their students as their own children. Aside from the aforementioned sacrifices, APSTs helped a lot by means of becoming the voice and the protection of the students. The educational system, particularly in the Philippines, is not comprehensive and does not usually create an environment that would make it engaging to those who are studying. When the school becomes insufficient in terms of providing necessary care for their students, some altruistic teachers often commit to such parental role sacrifice.

Sub-theme 3.1 Advocacy and Protection in Sensitive Situations

This act reflects an altruistic public-school teacher's deep empathy and selflessness, ensuring the student feels supported in a difficult moment, regardless of the behavior they've exhibited or the absence of formal structure.

["Wala siyang magulang kaya sabi ko kalimutan niyo po muna na ako po ay guro. Ako po muna ay guardian netong estudyanteng ito kahit siya yung nam-bully. Nangailangan ako mag-adjust. Alam ko hindi dapat ganito ang sistema. Dapat, bata-bata lang, magulang-magulang. Kinailangan ko mangeelam."] – **APST2**

Further backing for this assertion comes from Harding et al. (2019), who describe teachers acting as promoters of students' welfare in circumstances of inequity. This core role was recognized in their research, which also characterized the genuine concerns raised by the teachers for student welfare through action; that is, by protecting students in an environment where institutional support was not properly given.

Sub-theme 3.2 Quasi-Parental Commitment

This goes beyond the usual teacher-student relationship and reflects a willingness to step into roles typically reserved for parents. In doing so, the teacher takes on an emotionally supportive and nurturing role, extending their care well beyond the academic duties of the classroom. Teachers who exhibit this level of commitment don't just teach; they actively engage with students on a personal level, ensuring their emotional and personal well-being.

["I stood as her parent, more than what I can offer just to help her."] – **APST3**

On the other hand, a notable and unexpected instance that emerged in the study, although not part of the original criteria, was the deeply moving story of the APST who supported a close student as they faced death. This incident underscores the extraordinary extent of altruism in educators, demonstrating how they take on responsibilities typically associated with parents or other close relatives.

["First time ko namatayan ng estudyante. Binigay sa akin siya ng magulang. Sabi sa akin ng magulang niya, ikaw na magbaba sa morgue kasi mas naging magulang ka pa dyan kesa sa akin. Sabi ko sakanya, kumapit ka, huling byahe na natin tong magkasama."] – **APST2**

APST2's statement highlights the teacher's extraordinary altruism, stepping into the role of a parent for the student, even in death. By accompanying the student's body

to the morgue, the teacher demonstrated a level of care and responsibility that transcended the usual teacher-student relationship. The teacher's words, "*kumapit ka, huling byahe na natin itong magkasama,*" reflect a deep, personal commitment to the student, showing that even in the most tragic circumstances, the teacher was willing to be there for the student as a guardian would. This act underscores an altruistic public-school teacher's willingness to provide support and compassion, even in the face of profound loss, showcasing the selflessness and dedication that define true altruism. Although this act was not part of the original research criteria, as it involved a deceased student, it reveals the profound emotional commitment that altruistic teachers have for their students, going beyond their professional duties and embodying a quasi-parental role in the most heartbreaking moments.

Research evidence clearly substantiates the conclusion about the actually quasi-parental function of the teachers. Kariou et al. (2021) posits that teachers become involved in "relational care" to support the students' emotional and personal growth including during crises. These roles often go beyond instructional support by taking parental responsibilities as we have noted in high-stress situations such as the students' health complications or cases of poor parenting at home.

RQ2. MOTIVATIONS OF ALTRUISTIC PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS

Central Theme 4: Awareness Towards Students' Struggles

Awareness of students' struggles were identified as critical in driving the motivation to help them beyond traditional teaching responsibilities. The APSTs emphasized the importance of recognizing students' unique challenges and developing personal connections to provide targeted, compassionate support. This awareness fueled a commitment to going above and beyond in supporting students.

Sub-theme 4.1 Understanding Students' Struggles

One key theme that emerged from the APSTs' responses is their deep sense of empathy in addressing students' emotional needs and well-being. APST1 expresses sympathy for students, indicating an emotional response to their difficulties.

["Nakakaawa din yung bata.."] – APST1

On a similar note, APST3 highlights how empathy and compassion drive their actions, becoming more aware of students' struggles.

["What drives me to help is my empathy and compassion... You became aware that they're struggling"] – APST3

Furthermore, APST4, too, points out that it is critical to realize the underlying reasons for the behaviors of students, so that early intervention and support can also benefit those involved.

["Being able to know their reasons behind their actions, and empathize that they're struggling at an early age"] – APST4

This finding aligns with the theoretical framework of the present study, which draws upon Daniel Batson's (2015) Empathy-Altruism hypothesis. Research has shown that teachers who are aware of students' struggles are better able to provide the emotional and academic support needed for success. As Greenslade (2020) suggests, teachers who practice empathy can create stronger, more supportive relationships with their students, fostering an environment that encourages growth and learning. Essentially, Barton and Garvis (2019) differentiate empathy and compassion, defining empathy as the ability of teachers to understand a student's feelings, while compassion is defined more in terms of attitude with an even greater commitment to action. Knowing a student's background and challenges allows teachers to extend unique support for that student, addressing their academic and emotional needs. The studies mentioned above corroborate the view that empathy is a key aspect of crafting strong relationships between teachers and students, thus facilitating altruism.

Sub-theme 4.2 Building Personal Connections

Meanwhile, APST2 underscored the importance of recognizing and addressing each student's unique circumstances, aligning with the broader educational understanding of individualized support.

["Alam ko naman kasi yung pangangailangan kasi ng estudyante"] – APST2

This aligns with Wang's (2023) study, which links the cultivation of positive teacher-student relationships to teacher mindfulness and emotional intelligence. It indicates that emotional intelligence acts as the mediating factor between mindfulness and teacher-student interactions; this means that the teachers appear not only to be mindful but also emotionally aware with regard to addressing different emotional needs of their students.

Central Theme 5: Dedication to Support

APST's dedication to supporting students extends beyond academic duties. highlights how public-school teachers see their role not just as educators but as advocates for students' well-being. This dedication fosters an environment where students feel understood and cared for.

Sub-theme 5.1 Responding to Needs

APST5 emphasize the importance of responding to students' emotional needs, recognizing that offering support when students require it is a keyway to demonstrate care. By reaching out and providing emotional support, these teachers prioritize students' well-being alongside their academic needs. This act of reaching out fosters trust and strengthens the teacher-student relationship, creating an environment where students feel valued and understood. Altruistic public-school teachers believe that addressing

emotional needs is crucial, ultimately motivating students to engage more fully in both their emotional and academic growth.

["Reaching out to them when they need support is a way to show that I care."]

– APST5

A study by Francis & Pratheesh (2024) found that teachers who engage with students on a personal level and provide tailored support whether emotional or behavioral help create an environment that encourages students to thrive. Such teachers are perceived as more approachable and caring, which leads to increased student motivation and a stronger sense of belonging within the classroom. In addition, Li (2024) highlighted that when teachers provide consistent and thoughtful support, students feel more capable and confident, which contributes to better academic performance and overall well-being. These findings align with the sentiments expressed by the APSTs in this study, where reaching out and responding to students' needs is seen not only as a way to provide assistance but as a meaningful gesture to show care.

Central Theme 6: Personal Influence and Experience

The personal experiences of APSTs significantly influence their motivation to help their students.

Sub-theme 6.1 Relating Through Personal Experience

Public-school teachers who have faced their own struggles or have been recipients of support often feel to "pay it forward" and offer the same kind of support to their students, as they relate personally to the struggles students face.

["Nakikita ko ngayon sarili ko dun sa sitwasyon. Kasi kung ako, sobrang hirap ng buhay talaga namin eh kaya Kapag may pagkakataon, gusto ng estudyante ko, nagustuhan mo yan, bibilhin natin yan. gusto mo, dagdagan natin yan. Tara, bibilhin natin yan."] – **APST2**

Research herewith would strengthen the view that, in general, personal experience is motivating educators to become helpful toward their students. LaRusso et al. (2021) argue that teachers who have had similar experiences due to some hard times in their lives appear to be much more caring toward those students undergoing similar experiences. These teachers are likely to develop individualized supports not only on the academic front but also on emotional and social grounds

Sub-theme 6.2 Giving Back Through Experience

Drawing from their own experiences of hardship, these altruistic public-school teachers feel a deep sense of responsibility to support students facing similar struggles. Their focus is not on receiving something in return but rather on fostering a culture of kindness and generosity, encouraging students to extend help to others. This altruistic mindset creates an environment where students can grow emotionally.

["Hindi mo kailangan bumawi sa akin. Bumawi ka sa iba.."] – APST2

According to UNESCO IIEP (2019), teachers with personal experience are highly involved in creating a surrounding that promotes student development. Similarly, it was found by Martinsone & Žydžiūnaite (2023) underlined that the social-emotional competence and well-being of teachers are highly important concerning the establishment of positive relationships with students. Teachers who have emotional and psychological support are more likely to give emotional and psychological support to students concerning students' well-being.

RQ3. CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH ALTRUISTIC BEHAVIORS EXHIBITED BY PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS

Central Theme 7: Emotional and Relational Complexities

The researchers found from the APSTs' responses that one of the significant challenges faced by altruistic public-school teachers is the lack of involvement and cooperation from parents.

Sub-theme 7.1 Parental Involvement and Cooperation

The absence of parental involvement places an added burden on teachers, who are left to compensate for this gap by providing additional emotional and personal support to their students. This issue is very difficult for altruistic public-school teachers as they are impacted by the sense of responsibility and commitment to their students. However, when parents are disengaged or not cooperative, it complicates the teacher's ability to provide the best possible care and guidance for his charges; hence the job becomes more demanding and drawn, emotionally.

["Yung pinaka problema talaga dito ay yung mga magulang. Minsan hindi sila cooperative. Kung ano lang yung madali para sa kanila, yun ang gagawin nila."]

– APST1

["I saw her parents post that, which seemed to show the opposite situation that really disappoints me because to me, parents should be the one that really supports their children."] – **APST4**

Chen et al. (2023) shows a great part of the involvement of parents in student engagement and academic growth. The study argues that students with parents' active involvement in their studies are prone to better outcomes in motivation, school adjustment, and better performance. It also points out that many parents drag themselves from engaging meaningfully due to different barriers- be it lack of time, resources, or something else deeper. That does greatly affect students' progress, as all teachers cannot fill in for the lost home-school collaboration in all cases.

Alghamdi & Sideridis (2023) further supports this by demonstrating that critically low levels of parental engagement are linked to abrupt and unpredictable levels of teacher burnout. Using a cusp catastrophe model, the study found that when parental

disengagement is high, essential supports are withdrawn, leading to increased emotional strain on teachers. Thus, the lack of parental involvement not only impacts student outcomes but also places an unsustainable burden on teachers, particularly those who already go beyond their roles to support their students.

This disconnect becomes a significant challenge for altruistic teachers, who often take on the role of a "secondary parent," attempting to fill in the gaps left by insufficient parental involvement. In these cases, teachers must navigate the complexities of providing both academic and emotional support, further intensifying the demands of their role.

Sub-theme 7.2 Parental Expectations and Jealousy

The emotional and psychological effects of parental expectations and jealousy present another significant challenge for altruistic public-school teachers. The situation becomes even more complex for altruistic public-school teachers, who, despite their best intentions to support the student's well-being, may find themselves facing resentment from parents, making the act of altruism even more challenging.

["Ang bago ngayon is, nag seselos na magulang. Yun ang medyo nahirapan ako. Ang hirap, sobrang hirap talaga. Sabi niya, huling beses mo nang bibilhan ng ganito. Ang sakit sa akin"] – APST2

Supporting this concern, studies show that parental jealousy can undermine not only the teacher-student relationship but also the child's mental and emotional development (Van Der Wal, 2020). When parental jealousy goes unchecked, it may prevent parents from offering the necessary support that fosters a child's academic and emotional well-being, further complicating the educational environment. The emotional burden on both teachers and students, as they try to balance academic success with complex family dynamics, highlights the need for teachers to develop strategies to manage such challenges while maintaining a positive learning environment.

Sub-theme 7.3 Emotional and Psychological Response

APST2 discussed the emotional strain of helping or being altruistic, particularly when teachers face a lack of understanding from others regarding their efforts to support students emotionally. This highlights how some people fail to recognize the emotional investment that altruistic teachers make in their students. For APST2, the emotional toll of teaching becomes even more difficult when their efforts are not acknowledged or understood, making it harder to cope with the weight of their students' emotional struggles.

["Ang pinakamahirap. Personally, ang pinakamahirap talaga dyan is yung mindset ng iba na hindi ganun ang pagtulong"] – APST2

Meanwhile, APST5 emphasized the overwhelming challenge of balancing the academic and emotional needs of students. Altruistic public-school teachers often absorb their students' personal struggles, which leads to emotional exhaustion.

["Balancing time and emotional exhaustion. It's also difficult to take on their problems because I end up carrying them myself."] – APST5

APST2 also highlighted the challenge of dealing with students who take advantage of their altruistic nature. It underscores the vulnerability of teachers who selflessly give their time and energy, only to experience disregard or manipulation in return.

["Sinasantala talaga, yung mabait ka, yung abusado,"] – APST2

According to Herman et al. (2018) the emotional strain of attending to students' emotional demands is the root cause of teacher burnout and emotional fatigue. Increased stress and burnout are caused by teachers' tendency to internalize their students' difficulties. High levels of stress have been shown to have a detrimental impact on teachers' health and their ability to deliver high-quality instruction since they affect how they interact with their students.

Sub-theme 7.4 Using Personal Financial Resources

APST1 and APST5 shared experiences highlighting the financial sacrifices teachers make to meet the personal needs of their students. Teachers often go beyond their official duties, using their own money to help cover school-related expenses, such as providing supplies or addressing students' financial difficulties.

["Minsan kailangan mong maglabas ng pera mo para makatulong."] – APST1

["There was even a time when I had to borrow money just so I could provide for my student."] – APST5

The use of personal financial resources by teachers to support their students is an increasingly recognized challenge, with significant emotional and practical consequences. According to Alibang (2023), many teachers, particularly in public schools, often face financial strain due to low wages and insufficient school funding, which can lead them to spend their own money on classroom supplies, educational materials, or even helping students directly. This additional financial burden adds to the emotional and psychological stress experienced by teachers. Studies have shown that financial stress among educators can negatively impact their health, job satisfaction, and overall productivity. Financial stress has been linked to symptoms such as irritability, anxiety, fatigue, and poor sleep, which, in turn, can contribute to burnout.

Furthermore, Ferrer (2017) highlights the persistent financial struggles faced by public-school teachers in the Philippines, revealing that many are burdened by debt and lack access to effective financial education. The study notes that despite their regular income, numerous teachers resort to loans—often from informal lenders—just to meet daily expenses or fund classroom needs aligning with the experience of APST5. This financial strain not only affects their personal well-being but also compromises their professional performance and morale. In the context of altruistic teachers, this challenge becomes even more pronounced, as these educators frequently use personal funds to support students or improve classroom conditions. When financial stability is lacking, the emotional and psychological burden of selfless teaching becomes even harder to sustain.

Central Theme 8: Community Perception and Misunderstandings

The researchers found that in the context of public education, altruistic teachers face challenges beyond the classroom, including the misinterpretation of their actions by community members.

Sub-theme 8.1 Misinterpretations of Intentions

Reflecting the challenge of their altruistic efforts being misinterpreted, which adds emotional strain to their already demanding roles as public-school teachers.

["Yung iba nilalagyan ng malisya. Problema talaga yung pananaw ng iba."]

– APST2

["Some people in the community misinterpreted and misunderstood my actions, thinking that I had an intimate relationship with the student."] – **APST3**

Participants such as APST2 and APST3 shared experiences where their genuine support for students was misunderstood, leading to suspicions about their professional conduct. These misunderstandings not only create reputational challenges but also add emotional strain, reflecting the community's lack of understanding of teachers' professional boundaries and further complicating their altruistic behavior toward students.

According to Fang (2021) teacher engagement and relationship-building are vital for student success. However, these same interactions can lead to misunderstandings, especially when teachers are seen engaging closely with students in a caring manner, which could be perceived as favoritism or inappropriate behavior by others. Additionally, teachers may face public scrutiny, which adds to their emotional burden and affects their professional reputation and relationships within the community.

Central Theme 9: Resources Inconsistency

This challenge was emphasized as a critical barrier for altruistic public-school teachers in their efforts to help less privileged students, as the APST noted the significant difficulties they face due to insufficient resources and lack of institutional support.

Sub-theme 9.1 Lack of Resources and Support

The researchers found that this inconsistency in resources and support is a pervasive issue, as some schools are well-funded while others are not, creating disparities in the quality of education.

["Sa public schools, paminsan- minsan, depende sa school, may budget, minsan wala."] – **APST1**

Research on financial stress among teachers shows similar effects, underscoring its impact on both their professional and personal well-being. Teachers who face financial insecurity often experience heightened stress levels, leading to decreased job satisfaction and performance. A study by Dizon-Ross et al. (2019) revealed that teachers in high-cost

areas are more prone to financial anxiety, which can lead to negative attitudes about their work, increased absenteeism, and a higher likelihood of leaving the profession. The inconsistency in school budgets mirrors these broader financial pressures, highlighting the emotional and mental toll on teachers. Inconsistent financial support, as seen in APST1's experience, exacerbates stress, burnout, and challenges in providing for their students' well-being.

Central Theme 10: Professionalism and Boundaries

This central theme was emphasized by the APSTs, highlighting the challenges altruistic public-school teachers face in maintaining professional conduct amidst various external forces.

Sub-theme 10.1 Maintaining Professional Boundaries

APST2 emphasized that one of the biggest challenges they face as an altruistic public-school teacher is the perception of their colleagues, particularly when it comes to professionalism. This highlights how the teacher's effort to help can sometimes be perceived negatively, further complicating their selfless role of being altruistic.

["Ang pinakamalaking hamon talaga is yung pananaw talaga ng mga kasama ko pa, professionally. Yung sila din, sila yung pinaka malaking hamon."] – APST2

In the context of teaching, when a teacher's genuine efforts to support students are misunderstood or criticized by colleagues, it can diminish their motivation and create a sense of isolation. Moreover, workplaces that lack recognition and trust, such as schools where professional collaboration is limited, can cause teachers to feel disconnected, leading to burnout and emotional exhaustion. Studies by Lowery (2025) further highlight the critical role of leadership empathy and active support in addressing such challenges. When school leadership fails to foster an inclusive, collaborative culture, or neglects to support teachers during times of professional difficulty, it contributes to teachers feeling undervalued. This, in turn, exacerbates stress and burnout, making it even harder for altruistic teachers to navigate the emotional and mental strain of maintaining their professionalism while caring deeply for their students.

One significant theme that emerged, however, was not part of the analysis, from the researcher's interviews was the profound trauma experienced by following the death of a student.

["Nagkaroon ako ng trauma doon sa estudyante kong namatay."] – APST2

For these teachers, the trauma is compounded by their strong sense of responsibility and commitment to their students' well-being. They often see themselves as caregivers, and when a student dies under their care, it amplifies feelings of guilt, failure, and helplessness. This emotional burden highlights the need for adequate support for teachers facing such traumatic experiences. Altruistic teachers, due to their emotional investment, may struggle more with grief and trauma compared to those who are more

detached, making it essential for educational institutions to provide mental health resources.

Apgar et al. (2022) highlight the significant psychological toll that trauma, particularly student loss or trauma, can take on educators. Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) and Compassion Fatigue (CF) are common among teachers, especially those working with children exposed to trauma. These educators often carry the emotional weight of their students' suffering, which can lead to burnout, mental health issues, and decreased job satisfaction. Similarly, Arksey et al. (2022) explore how teachers' bereavement experiences, following the violent death of a student, are both personal and professional, noting that collegial support and follow-up counseling are crucial for healing and addressing ongoing emotional needs.

Although this study did not delve deeply into the trauma experienced by APSTs due to grief from a student, it underscores the need for future research to explore how these heavy events impact teachers' mental health, particularly for altruistic teachers. Further exploration is essential to understand how their emotional investment and sense of responsibility contribute to the intensity of their trauma and to identify effective interventions that can support them in the healing process.

RQ4. HOW PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS HANDLE THE CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH ALTRUISTIC BEHAVIORS

Central Theme 11: Community Engagement and Collaboration

As the saying goes, no man is an island, and for altruistic public-school teachers, collaboration is one of the keys to handle challenges that were previously mentioned in the analysis above.

Sub-theme 11.1 Building Partnerships

APST1 and APST3 highlighted the importance of reaching out to others for support.

["Usually, yung challenge talaga dyan sa pagtulong ay yung sa financial part. Kaya ang ginagawa ay nagtapat ka rin ng ibang tao, kahit sa mga kapatid mo, para tumulong."] – APST1

"Humingi rin ako ng tulong sa guidance counselor para masubaybayan nang mabuti ang estudyanteng iyon." – APST3

Research supports these findings, showing that schools with strong collaborative practices, such as those integrating social and emotional learning (SEL) programs, significantly improve student engagement and learning outcomes. Schools with well-implemented SEL programs, often supported by partnerships with families and community professionals, report higher levels of student interest in learning and improved academic outcomes. (Social and Emotional Learning in U.S. Schools - CASEL, 2024)

Central Theme 12: Open-Mindedness

This central theme allows public-school teachers to approach challenges incorporated with being altruistic through empathy, understanding, and a non-judgmental perspective regarding on their students' situation.

Sub-theme 12.1 Being Open to Student's Struggles

This emphasizes the importance of maintaining an open heart towards students' personal struggles.

["I try to keep an open mind and heart to understand what they are going through."]

– APST5

According to a study by Abacioğlu et al. (2020), teachers' multicultural attitudes and perspective-taking abilities significantly influence their effectiveness in responding to students' diverse needs. When teachers are open to understanding the unique challenges that students from different cultural backgrounds face, they are better equipped to provide the support necessary for holistic development. This research highlights that teachers who approach their students' struggles with empathy and an open mind are more likely to create inclusive environment that respect and respond to the diverse social, emotional, needs of less privileged students.

Central Theme 13: Emotional and Resource Management

Altruistic public-school teachers must maintain between managing their own resources both emotional and material while still having the capability to help students. This theme is often seen in educators or individuals in helping professions who, despite facing their own struggles, continue to help students.

Sub-theme 13.1 Balancing Personal Struggles

Altruistic public-school teachers handle challenges by managing their own personal struggles while maintaining a stable and supportive persona for those they are assisting. They often face the emotional challenge of balancing their own difficulties with the need to be there for their students.

["Managing what I have left. Tsaka yung mga tinutulungan ko din naman alam din nila yung sitwasyon ko, kaya kailangan ko mag mukhang stable kasi hindi magsasabi

minsan at minsan malala talaga tapos manghihinayang ka na sana natulungan mo siya sa pagkakataon na yon.] – APST2

This aligns with recent research that emphasizes the emotional labor of maintaining a facade of stability. Fang et al. (2024) found that individuals in caregiving or support roles often experience compassion fatigue, a state of emotional depletion caused by constant exposure to the struggles of others. This emotional labor becomes even more challenging when communication barriers prevent those in need from openly seeking

help, placing the onus on supporters to anticipate and respond to unspoken needs trusted connections. This dynamic place additional pressure to interpret unspoken cues, heightening their emotional toll.

Central Theme 14: Student-Centered Support

This theme shows that altruistic teachers remain committed to addressing students' needs and goals, allowing them to manage their own challenges by dedicating themselves to student welfare. This focus on helping students becomes a keyway for these teachers to navigate and overcome the challenges they face.

Sub-theme 14.1 Prioritizing Students' Needs

Prioritizing students' needs is reflected in APST4's statement which emphasizes the teacher's commitment to helping students despite the challenges they face as altruistic educators. Even though they experience emotional burdens and personal struggles, these teachers choose to focus on their primary goal: assisting students in need. This focus on helping students allows them to navigate through difficulties, as they are driven by a strong sense of purpose and dedication to their students' well-being, making their challenges more manageable.

["I just focus on the goal of really helping them."] – APST4

Daniels et al. (2024) highlights how teachers remain focused on supporting their students, even when facing challenges. Research shows that teachers use a variety of methods to keep students motivated and engaged, especially when dealing with difficulties like adapting to new teaching methods or having fewer resources. These strategies include helping students feel more in control of their learning, encouraging their abilities, and building strong connections with them. These approaches aim to meet both the academic and emotional needs of students. Teachers continue to prioritize these aspects of support, ensuring a positive learning environment despite any obstacles.

RQ5. EMERGING THEMES

The exploration of the lived experiences of altruistic public-school teachers (APSTs) revealed fourteen (14) central themes, each encompassing unique sub-themes that highlight the multifaceted nature of their roles.

These emerging themes illustrate the depth of APSTs' awareness of students' struggles and their unwavering dedication to meeting both personal needs beyond academics. APSTs often drew upon personal experiences to foster genuine connections, while also making significant financial, material, time, and personal sacrifices. Some assumed quasi-parental roles, advocating for students in sensitive situations and navigating emotional and relational complexities involving families. Misunderstandings from the community, inconsistent resources, and the need to maintain professionalism further complicated their responsibilities. Despite these challenges, APSTs remained

open-minded and student-centered, engaging with the broader community to build support systems and continuously balancing their own emotional well-being with the demands of their altruistic commitment. These themes collectively underscore the resilience, compassion, and profound impact of APSTs who prioritize student welfare above all else.

RQ6. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Based on the findings of the study, it has become evident that altruistic public-school teachers face numerous challenges that significantly affect their well-being—particularly emotional burnout, financial strain, and issues related to professionalism—largely due to their selfless commitment to serving underprivileged students. In response to these experiences, the researchers proposed the **Altruistic Teacher Assistance (ALTA)** as a framework designed to address the specific needs of altruistic teachers.

Figure 1. Altruistic Teacher Assistance (ALTA) framework

While ALTA is not a program directly implemented by the researchers, it stands as a research-driven and comprehensive framework that can be adopted by relevant stakeholders. It provides a structured response to the core issues identified in this study, offering support for altruistic public-school teachers (APSTs) through integrated components such as mental health care, financial support, professional safeguards, community collaboration, and recognition mechanisms. The ultimate goal of the framework is to promote the holistic well-being of these teachers.

This proposed framework is intended for adoption by future researchers and operationalization by key stakeholders, including the Department of Education (DepEd), school administrators, mental health professionals, and related institutions. The researchers acknowledge that these stakeholders possess the appropriate authority, resources, and expertise required to implement the framework effectively. With their collaboration, the vision of empowering and supporting altruistic educators can become a sustainable reality.

The framework is fundamentally anchored in the most central support mechanism for providing uninterrupted emotional and psychological support to APSTs known as **Teacher Wellness Hub (TWH)**. This encompasses virtual therapy, stress management workshops, and peer-led support groups that form an integral portion in building mental resilience and combating burnout. These activities will be offered quarterly during an initial pilot phase, with implementation facilitated by school administrators and licensed mental health professionals. Resources needed include a secure virtual platform and a panel of trained volunteer counselors. In terms of results, the anticipated outcome is a significant improvement in the well-being of APSTs and a decrease in emotional exhaustion.

The **Financial Relief Program** is intended to address the economic challenges that frequently undermine the sustainability of altruistic teaching. This includes the initiation of annual fundraising campaigns and also the establishment of a small grant fund for resourcing classroom expenses or urgent needs in their selfless dedication. Implementation will involve engagement with school administrators, local community leaders, and NGOs. Its core resource shall comprise a trusted crowdfunding platform and a reliable system to maintain the flow of donation. It will cover the timely need for financial relief aimed at enabling APSTs to be focused, stable, and dedicated without needing to incur those costs personally.

Another crucial aspect of the framework is the **Empowerment and Protection Policy**, which is geared towards establishing institutional policies that protect APSTs' mental, emotional, and professional boundaries. The policy includes policy formation and awareness programs for the parents and the school community. Supervised by school authorities, DepEd, and legal consultants, this component will be augmented through empirical research and consultations with stakeholders. The desired outcome is to strengthen the institutional protection and improve working conditions for APSTs' well-being.

To encourage collaborative support between families and schools, the **Parent-Teacher Engagement** program has been proposed. This initiative promotes shared accountability in nurturing students' academic and personal growth. Activities include biannual parent-teacher conferences and co-facilitated workshops involving APSTs, administrators, parents, and mental health professionals. Key resources will include workshop materials, communication platforms, and facilitation tools. The main resources will be the workshop materials, communication platform tools, and facilitation tools with the outcome expected to strengthen the APST's emotional and social support networks in the cooperative and caring school climate.

The ***Beacon of Altruism Awards*** is the final component of the framework, designed to recognize and celebrate the unwavering dedication of APSTs. It features a structured nomination and selection process, an annual awards ceremony, and professional development grants for awardees. This initiative will be conducted at the end of each academic year in collaboration with the Department of Education (DepEd) and local stakeholders. Required resources include a nomination system, event planning logistics, and sponsor contributions. The objective is to reinforce the value of altruism in education, inspire continued commitment, and elevate the status of APSTs.

The success of the program will be monitored through the following strategies:

1. Conduct bi-annual surveys/tests to measure the mental health, emotional well-being, and satisfaction level of APSTs.
2. Regular focus group discussions will be conducted with participating APSTs to assess the effectiveness of each component of the program.
3. Regular reviews will be held with community partners to evaluate their involvement and the program's success in engaging the broader community.
4. Long-term tracking of program outcomes to provide for sustainability and continued relevance in responding to the needs of APSTs.
5. Program components will be refined based on feedback from APSTs and stakeholders for continuous improvement.

Given the nature of public schools—where budget availability can vary significantly—the ALTA framework was designed with flexibility in mind. It can be scaled and adapted according to the capacity of each school, allowing for partial implementation where necessary. While the researchers do not have the authority or resources to directly implement the framework, ALTA serves as a structured, research-based foundation that stakeholders like DepEd, school heads, and partner organizations can adopt and customize based on their context.

Although ALTA is a proposed framework and not yet an implemented program, the researchers strongly believe in its potential to foster APSTs' resilience and well-being. It is hoped that through the adoption of this framework, the Department of Education (DepEd) and related educational institutions will be able to cultivate a more supportive, empowered, and sustainable environment for altruistic behaviors among such contexts.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis of the study, the participants' testimonies regarding on being an altruistic public-school teacher have led to the following conclusions:

1. The researchers' analysis of the lived experiences reveals that altruistic teachers are motivated by a deep sense of empathy and shaped by their interactions with students and their work environment to addressing the unique needs of their students, particularly those from less privileged backgrounds. These teachers often go beyond their professional responsibilities, offering emotional, academic, and material support to ensure students' well-being.
2. Challenges include emotional and relational complexities, such as dealing with uncooperative and jealous parents, managing personal emotional and financial strain, lack of resources and support within school institution, balancing the emotional toll of supporting students while maintaining professional boundaries due to misinterpretation of intentions, and dealing with situations where some students themselves abuse their teachers' kindness and take advantage of their selflessness. These difficulties highlight the profound emotional burden carried by altruistic teachers in their efforts to help less privileged students.
3. While altruism fosters genuine care and dedication, it often comes at a personal cost, leading to burnout and emotional exhaustion. Therefore, promoting healthy altruism is crucial—altruism that includes balance and proper support systems. Sustaining altruistic behavior requires ensuring that it does not come at the expense of personal well-being.
4. To address these challenges, the researchers propose the *Altruistic Teacher Assistance (ALTA)* framework, a flexible, research-based model designed to support the well-being of altruistic teachers. Grounded in Batson's Empathy-Altruism Theory (1991), the framework acknowledges the psychological, emotional, and professional toll of sustained altruism. It includes components like mental health care, financial relief, professional protection, and recognition, aimed at preventing burnout and fostering resilience. Although not implemented directly, ALTA is intended for adoption by stakeholders such as DepEd, school administrators, and NGOs, with flexibility to adapt to varying school resources.

Recommendations

The following recommendations provide valuable insights for various beneficiaries—altruistic teachers, parents, students, communities, school institutions, stakeholders, present and future researchers.

For APSTs. Altruistic teachers should prioritize mental well-being by seeking regular support from peers, mentors, or counseling. Setting boundaries while still supporting students is vital to maintaining balance. Regular self-reflection, professional development, and collaboration with school leaders can prevent burnout. Using the ALTA framework's mental health resources and workshops can also help manage emotional strain.

For Parents. Parents should stay aware of their children's challenges, especially in underserved communities, and recognize the extra efforts made by altruistic teachers. Maintaining open, supportive communication with teachers can ease their burden. Advocating for teacher support creates a more nurturing and sustainable learning environment.

For School Institutions. Schools must offer resources that address emotional, material, and professional needs. Reducing teachers' personal burden through resilience programs and a supportive culture is essential. Adopting models like ALTA can integrate mental health support into school systems and acknowledge the value of teachers' altruistic efforts.

For Researchers. Researchers should continue develop action plans to share findings on altruistic public-school teachers' experiences. Webinars and academic conferences can engage educators, policymakers, and the public in meaningful dialogue, raising awareness of their emotional challenges and highlighting solutions like the ALTA framework. Broad engagement will foster deeper exploration and collaboration in this vital field.

For Future Researchers. Future research should examine the emotional and psychological challenges altruistic teachers face, especially trauma from events like student loss. Understanding these experiences can guide policies that support healing and sustain their work. Investigating coping strategies and the long-term viability of frameworks like ALTA is essential to protect teachers' mental health.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers declare that this study has been conducted following ethical standards without any deviations. Consent was taken from all the respondents, who were given the assurance of the option to withdraw anytime without repercussions. The confidentiality of the respondents was diligently kept ensuring their anonymity and well-being during the whole research process.

The researchers assert that no conflict of interest was present in conducting this study. Furthermore, researchers have avoided all forms of plagiarism and bias in interpreting the results. The results of the research are purely for research purposes, adhering to maintain the high standards of academic integrity.

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